

**METHODOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL
READING TEXTBOOKS ON TOPICS**

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Annotation: The article examinations - the dynamic development of science, technology and technology, the rapid growth of culture, art and literature in the context of mental and spiritual maturation of children. It requests the use of new methods and techniques in the educational sphere, in particular, the widespread use of types of work that develop students' skills of independent creative thinking and speech. The work on speech development is diverse. The teacher should help students to acquire speech knowledge, skills and abilities in their native language, teach them to skillfully use the acquired skills in practice.

Keywords: Speech development, work on text, oral and written speech, communication, word meaning, speech.

As you know, in the system of continuing education, textbooks are the main didactic tool. "The textbook is a book in which the foundations of relevant science are laid out on the basis of achievements of modern science and culture, and meets the goals and objectives of Education. It is, on the one hand, the primary source of knowledge for students, and on the other hand, the primary medium of instruction". The textbook is also considered "the main and leading type of educational literature, which lays out the foundations of knowledge in a particular discipline in a certain order and is written at a high spiritual-ideological, scientific-methodological level" [8].

Any textbook material is mastered through the independent activities of the student based on the teacher's assignment. Work on textbooks covers the following issues related to the educational activities of students includes:

1) to understand the goals and objectives envisaged from mastering the subject of Study; 2) to master the general characteristics of the textbook material; 3) to record the knowledge and concepts acquired in the educational process.

It is understandable that the graphical solution to each of these issues related to working on textbooks should not repeat each other, of course.

Teaching literacy, Reading, and early teaching to write is an important aspect of native language learning and serves as a distinctive introduction to

Language Teaching. The textbooks" Alphabet "and the subsequent" reading book " should also reveal to students the wealth and beauty of their native language.

It is known that any knowledge is acquired through the reading of texts belonging to certain areas. Elementary grade "reading book" textbooks are no exception. The texts in the current 1st [6] and 2nd grade [7] "reading book" textbooks belong to different literary genres, which are given in a mixed way.

It seems that the texts in textbooks belong to such a variety of literary genres as popular text, poetry, song, story, fairy tale, narrative, parable. At this point, we also want to dwell on the survey conducted among primary students and its results. What texts do you like the most in the textbook "reading book" in order to determine which genre of works we 2nd graders like the most? We distributed a questionnaire with the question" mark them " and received the results as follows:

The results showed that the majority of Primary School students were not yet able to distinguish texts by genre. Therefore, the results obtained are in some way relative. But it is also advisable to choose the texts included in the" reading book "textbooks as part of the students' interest.

Understanding and understanding textbook materials, working with the author's text will allow readers to master the views of others and gradually create their own views. Therefore, the texts in the textbooks of the "reading book" of elementary grades should also correspond in volume and content to the level of development of students and the requirements for the upbringing of a harmonious generation. When the lexical and grammatical loading in the text increases, it becomes more complicated to understand. Therefore, in these textbooks, the amount of new words is required to be limited.

In the later stages of education, as the vocabulary of students becomes richer, the volume of texts increases and the content becomes more complex. Excerpts from works of art are given a wide place. This teaches us to understand and apply Model speech.

Noted psychologist D.B.Elkonin believes that the leading feature of educational activities is determined by the fact that the student acquires the qualification of subordinating his work in various activities to mandatory rules for everyone as a social system. Obedience to the rules creates in the reader the skill of managing his own behavior, and at the same time even higher forms of voluntary management of behavior. According to the author, educational activities have the following structural structure: 1) educational tasks; 2) educational activities; 3) supervision; 4) assessment. This activity is primarily

due to the fact that primary school students acquire theoretical knowledge, that is, knowledge in which the main features of the studied academic discipline are highlighted. When solving educational tasks, students occupy common ways of chambering in such relationships. Training will focus on mastering exactly these methods.

The textbooks of the "reading book" of primary classes, which are used in practice, give the impression that, through the means of samples of fiction, they serve to formulate the correct, fast, fluent, conscious and expressive reading skills in students, to state information about nature and socio-political dates, rather than educate their artistic-aesthetic taste. The fact that for several decades a large place has been allocated for popular and artistic texts on the seasons of the year in all the textbooks of the 1st-4th grade "reading book" is clear evidence of our opinion expressed above.

The theoretical analysis carried out on the textbooks of the 1st and 2nd grade "reading book", which were used in practice, caused the birth of a number of other questions. Including:

1. Can all the materials presented in the textbook satisfy the ideological and didactic requirements for speech cultivation, which are recorded in the state educational standard of primary education?

2. Do textual questions serve to reveal the content and essence of texts?

3. The task of the textbook" reading book " is to form the artistic and aesthetic taste of students, educate them spiritually and morally, whether it is just a pand-exhortation or by instilling love for the book enriching their worldview?

In our opinion, the textbooks of the 1st and 2nd grade "reading book", which are used and used in educational practice, cannot satisfactorily answer these questions ideologically - aesthetically.

In our opinion, the reasons for this are as follows (on the example of the 2nd grade textbooks, which are used in practice):

1. Most of the texts in the textbook are artificial by the authors of the book in a woven, emotionless and publicistic spirit. "Uzbekistan is my homeland", "autumn blessings", "book", " What are clothes sewn from?", "Be economical", among others, and this list can be continued again. "Works" of such content do not provide any spiritual feed for students who are just learning to read. Elementary students forcibly read texts that they did not enjoy themselves. However, it should be remembered that in compulsory education, the expected result cannot be achieved.

2. In some places, texts of the same content are listed in sequence. For example, "autumn", "autumn blessings", "autumn", etc. Such repetition makes classes a mandatory activity, even not counting the ideological-artistic level of texts.

3. Despite the fact that each section begins with several proverbs and riddles, artificial tissue riddles are also cited in many places. Methodically, Proverbs, riddles, quick sayings and dense delivery of poetic passages in this way, which are not aimed at a specific goal, lead to the formation of a superficial attitude towards them in readers. As a result, readers get bored in the process of working on the text. This condition leads to a deterioration in the quality of Education.

4. The texts of the "weather scrapers" given in the reading book "are suitable for the textbooks" the universe around us, texts such as "exhortation", "conversation etiquette", "etiquette for asking permission" are suitable for the textbook "etiquette".

5. The main part of the textual questions and tasks is structured in a shallow and shallow way, which in most cases are aimed only at determining the evidential information. There are also a lot of questions-assignments of the type "memorize a poem".

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